

Multiple Dissociation Constants and Free Energy Changes in Kaolinite and Bentonite Clays

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The electrochemical behaviour of clays is a method used for their classification. It is now known that pure clays like H-clays exist as partially substituted clays such as Al-H-clays etc. Hence a classification of kaolinite, bentonite or illite in partially substituted conditions can be established by a study of the dissociation constants of clay samples. Multiple dissociation constants are obtained, and a critical study of their values, leads to clay classification.

STUDY of the pH titration curves for different concentrations of H-Al clays, as suggested by Marshall¹ indicates that a strong or moderately strong acid function comes into play in the pH range 5 to 7. The rate of transformation from H-clay to Al-H clay has been studied by Coleman and Craig².

A number of attempts have been made³⁻⁷ to interpret the electrochemistry of clays by using dissociation constants, as is done for true solutions. Even when the pH curves show one inflection, a single dissociation constant is unsatisfactory over a wide range, hence two or more constants have been introduced. The free energy changes with the addition of sodium hydroxide can be found from potentiometric titrations. Here the reaction can be presented as :

and this reaction can be arranged according to the free energy changes which occur as neutralization progresses. It may be as follows :

In reaction 3 the free energy change per unit addition of alkali diminishes linearly with increase in initial pH. It can be calculated from the pH by the formula :

$$F_{(H)} = 1364(14.14 - \text{pH}), \text{ at } 25^\circ.$$

the convention being that one mole of hydroxyl ion in its standard state (normal solution) is added to an infinite amount of the clay system at the given pH. The incremental values for addition of sodium hydroxide began at 13,500 cal./equivalent, corresponding to a strongly acid function and were main-

tained upto 80 meq. base for a fresh H-resin treated clay.

Experimental

Samples nos. 1, 3 and 4 are kaolinitic clays and sample no. 2 is bentonitic clay. Potentiometric

TABLE I—POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION OF H-CLAY WITH NaOH

Sample no. 1: 10% Clay suspension (5.0 g clay in 50 ml distilled water)

NaOH 0.1N ml	Meq. of NaOH/100g. of clay	pH	$\Delta\text{pH}/\Delta v$	$\Delta F_{(H)}$, cals./mole
0.0	0.0	4.1	—	13694
0.1	0.2	4.5	4.00	13141
0.2	0.4	4.9	4.00	12603
0.3	0.6	5.0	1.00	12466
0.4	0.8	5.3	3.00	12057
0.5	1.0	5.6	3.00	11648
0.6	1.2	5.8	2.00	11375
0.8	1.6	6.1	1.50	10966
1.0	2.0	6.3	1.00	10693
1.2	2.4	6.5	1.00	10420
1.4	2.8	7.2	3.50	9738
1.6	3.2	7.9	3.50	8784
1.8	3.6	8.1	1.00	8238
2.0	4.0	8.6	2.50	8102
2.1	4.2	8.7	1.00	9657
2.3	4.6	9.3	3.00	7147
2.5	5.0	9.6	1.50	6192
2.7	5.4	9.9	1.50	5783
3.0	6.0	10.1	0.66	5510
3.3	6.6	10.2	0.33	5374
3.7	7.4	10.7	1.25	4692
4.5	9.0	10.9	0.25	4419
5.0	10.0	11.0	0.20	4282
6.0	12.0	11.2	0.20	4010
7.0	14.0	11.3	0.10	3874

TABLE 2—POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION OF H-CLAY WITH NaOH

Sample no. 2: 2.5% clay suspension (0.5 g clay in 20 ml distilled water)

NaOH 0.1N ml	Meq. of NaOH/100g. of clay	pH	$\Delta pH/\Delta v$	$\Delta F_{(H)}$ cal./mole
0.0	0.0	3.7	3.50	14240
0.1	2.0	4.0	3.50	13830
0.2	4.0	4.4	4.00	13285
0.3	6.0	—	—	—
0.4	8.0	5.0	3.00	12466
0.6	12.0	5.0	0.25	11784
0.8	16.0	5.7	1.00	11512
1.0	20.0	5.9	1.00	11239
1.4	28.0	6.3	1.00	10693
1.8	36.0	6.7	1.00	10148
1.9	38.0	6.8	0.50	10011
2.0	40.0	7.3	5.00	9339
2.2	44.0	8.2	4.50	8102
2.6	52.0	—	—	—
3.2	64.0	9.1	2.25	6874
3.4	68.0	9.9	4.00	5783
3.6	72.0	10.4	2.25	5101
3.8	76.0	10.7	1.50	4692
4.0	80.0	10.8	0.75	4556
4.5	90.0	11.1	0.80	4146
5.0	100.0	11.3	0.40	3874
5.5	110.0	11.4	0.30	3737

titrations of H-clays (< 0.002 mm) with 2.5% and 5% or 10% suspensions using 0.1N sodium hydroxide solution were carried out. The pH of the system was measured using Beckman pH meter. From these measurements, free energy changes and dissociation constants were calculated. For the sake of brevity, results for sample nos. 3 and 4 are omitted.

Results and Discussion

From the potentiometric titrations with sodium hydroxide, cation exchange capacity (CEC), disso-

ciation constants and free energy changes are found out. The results of calculated free energy changes and dissociation constants in Tables 3 and 4 show that sample nos. 1, 3 and 4 have pk values in the range 4.7 to 5.8 and free energy change values in the range of 13,800 to 9,738 cal/mole with first strong acid function.

The results of the calculated free energy changes in the beginning of potentiometric titration indicate that clay systems have a very strong acid function in the early stage. With the progress of neutralization, values for the free energy change with incremental addition of sodium hydroxide. These changes are in the agreement with dissociation constants. The first strong acid function was observed in the case of almost all clays. Second weak acid function in the $\Delta F_{(H)}$ range 9238 to 5647 cal./mole is observed for some of the clays. Base exchange capacities at the neutralization of this second weak acid function are considerably high. For few clay samples a very weak third acid function in $\Delta F_{(H)}$ range 8640 to 4692 cal./mole is observed. The pk_3 values obtained are high.

Drops in the $\Delta F_{(H)}$ values with addition of small quantities of sodium hydroxide, i.e., 5 to 10 meq. suggests that in clay systems, pure H-clay forms are not present. The probable reason for low values of $\Delta F_{(H)}$ in the early stages, is the presence and influence of Aluminium. From the results it was found that clays having 2nd and 3rd dissociation constants, the system will be in H₂-clay and H₃-clay forms respectively in the beginning of potentiometric titration. As titration proceeds the clay system changes and at the neutralization points which showed first and second strong acid functions, the clay systems will be in H-Al clay and H₂-Al clay forms respectively. At the neutralization point of second weak acid function, the clays will be in Al-clay or H-Al clay forms. When the Al-clay form exists in clay systems, it can be said that the system is saturated with Al and no acid function can be realised. For clays containing bentonite it was

TABLE 3—BASE EXCHANGE CAPACITIES AND $\Delta F_{(H)}$ FOR DIFFERENT CLAYS

Sample no.	At First inflection			At Second inflection			At Third inflection			At pH 7
	pH	Meq. NaOH/100 g. clay	$\Delta F_{(H)}$ cal./mole	pH	Meq. NaOH/100 g. clay	$\Delta F_{(H)}$ cal./mole	pH	Meq. NaOH/100 g. clay	$\Delta F_{(H)}$ cal./mole	Meq. NaOH/100 g. clay
1.	5.6	1.0	13694-11648	7.6	3.0	11648-9238	9.3	4.6	9238-7147	3.0
2.	7.3	40.0	14240-9330	9.9	68.0	9330-5738	—	—	—	38.0
3.	6.2	2.0	12466-10830	8.5	6.0	10830-7829	—	—	—	4.4
4.	6.2	2.0	13694-10830	9.5	6.0	10830-6329	—	—	—	2.6

TABLE 4—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS FOR DIFFERENT CLAYS

Sample no.	pk_1	k_2	pk_2	k_3	pk_3	k_3
1.	5.00	1.000×10^{-5}	6.30	5.012×10^{-7}	8.35	4.467×10^{-9}
2.	5.90	1.259×10^{-6}	8.40	2.512×10^{-9}	—	—
3.	5.75	1.778×10^{-6}	6.80	1.585×10^{-7}	—	—
4.	5.15	7.080×10^{-6}	8.25	5.624×10^{-9}	—	—

observed that the Al-clay form was attained after addition of as much as 60 meq. of base while for kaolinitic clays having considerable alumina, Al-clay forms are attained in the range 3.0 to 8.0.

From this the effect of aluminium on H-clay system becomes evident. Low base exchange capacities are thus accounted for on the basis of alumina content *i.e.*, higher the $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio higher will be the base exchange capacity.

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